

Diagnostic Accuracy of Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) Versus Histopathology in Thyroid LesionsShweta Joshi¹, Dilip Kumar²¹Senior Resident (Ex), Department of Pathology, Max Institute of Medical Sciences (MIMS), Max Hospital, Saket, South Delhi, India²Associate Director & Quality Manager, Max Lab, Max Superspeciality Hospital, Saket, South Delhi, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Objectives:** The present study was to compare the diagnostic accuracy of Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) versus Histopathology in patients of thyroid lesions.**Methods:** The cytology and histopathology slides were collected. Patient's clinical data was collected from the medical records. All the patients were reassured as to the simplicity and painlessness of the procedure and the patient was asked not to swallow while the needle is in the nodule. Patient was asked to rest in supine position with the head and neck extended over a pillow. The degree of extension should not produce skin tension that interferes with nodule palpation or partially obstructs vertebral artery blood flow in the elderly. The site of the needle puncture was cleaned by firm application of an alcohol swab. A 10 or 5mL syringe was used for obtaining cytologic specimens. 23 gauge needle were used. For nodules 1.5 cm or smaller, to and fro movements of the needle into the nodule were done. With larger nodules, peripheral subcapsular parts of the nodule were sampled rather than the center.**Results:** A total of 100 thyroid lesions cases were included. Most of the cases 32(32%) were in age group of 41-50 years. Male and female ratio was 1:4. According to FNAC diagnostic criteria, there were 62% benign cases, 9% malignant cases, 12% suspicious and 17% unsatisfactory or non-diagnosis. Out of 9 malignant lesions, papillary carcinoma was diagnosed in 5 cases, follicular carcinoma in 1 case, medullary carcinoma in 1 case and other malignancy present in 2 cases.**Conclusions:** the thyroid lesions are preponderance to old age female as compared to male population. FNAC is the best choice first line diagnostic test and effective screening tool for the diagnosis and management of patients with thyroid lesions.**Keywords:** Thyroid lesions, Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC), Histopathology.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Thyroid nodules have become more common these days with prevalence ranging from 4 to 7% in the general population [1]. The majority of these nodules are non-neoplastic or benign neoplasms. FNAC is done in cases of thyroid nodules to distinguish benign from malignant lesions. For proper management of thyroid nodules, they are classified as benign, malignant, suspicious, and insufficient for diagnosis. It helps to decide whether to treat thyroid nodules by surgery or not. The introduction of FNAC into the field of thyroid diagnostic tests has reduced unnecessary thyroid surgeries considerably. However, FNAC has some limitation such as specimen inadequacy and inaccurate sampling techniques [2].

Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is a cost – effective and a simple office procedure which gives a quick diagnosis at the first contact of the patient. It can delineate between benign and malignancy

and can be repeated for definite confirmation of diagnosis [3]. FNAC being a minimally invasive technique is particularly suitable in thyroid where an incisional biopsy may present problems. The lesions in thyroid are varied ranging from inflammation to neoplasm. FNAC of thyroid helps us to categorize the lesions which require surgical intervention and those which do not [4,5].

The National Cancer Institute (NCI) held the Thyroid FNAC State of the Science Conference in 2007, and its goal was to standardize diagnostic terminology, morphologic criteria, and risk of malignancy for reporting thyroid FNAC. The conference came up with a 6-tier system that they called The Bethesda System for Reporting the Thyroid Cytopathology (I = non-diagnostic, II=benign, III=atypia/follicular lesion of undetermined significance, IV = follicular neoplasm/suspicious for follicular neoplasm,

V=suspicious for malignancy, and VI=malignant) [6]. However, based only on the cytological examination of thyroid nodules, some follicular lesions are difficult to distinguish malignant from non-malignant entities, particularly the follicular adenoma from carcinoma [7]. Objectives of our study was to compared the diagnostic accuracy of Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) versus Histopathology in thyroid lesions.

Material & Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, Max Institute of Medical Sciences & Max Hospital, Saket South Delhi, India during a period from January 2024 to June 2024.

A total of 100 cases who presented with the history of swelling in midline of neck which were referred from the Departments of Surgery, Medicine & ENT for FNA procedure to the Department of Pathology at Max Institute of Medical Sciences & Max Hospital, Saket South Delhi were enrolled in the present study.

Patients who have had surgery, but FNAC was not performed preoperatively for thyroid swelling were excluded from the present study.

The cytology and histopathology slides were collected. Patient's clinical data was collected from the medical records. 1. Mental preparation: Proper mental preparation is the first step in the performance of FNAC. Most of the pain experienced by patients is minor discomfort magnified by anxiety.

All the patients were reassured as to the simplicity and painlessness of the procedure and the patient was asked not to swallow while the needle is in the nodule.

2. Physical examination: Patient was asked to rest in supine position with the head and neck extended over a pillow. The degree of extension should not produce skin tension that interferes with nodule palpation or partially obstructs vertebral artery blood flow in the elderly. The site of the needle puncture was cleaned by firm application of an alcohol swab.

Methods

A 10 or 5mL syringe was used for obtaining cytologic specimens. 23 gauge needle were used. For nodules 1.5 cm or smaller, to and fro movements of the needle into the nodule were done. With larger nodules, peripheral subcapsular parts of the nodule were sampled rather than the center. Minimum of three passes were done. Whenever fluid was obtained all the contents were aspirated and centrifuged. After aspiration, the needle is removed and the plunger is withdrawn. The needle is reattached, and the specimen is expressed onto the slide and then smeared with the edge of another slide. If particulate matter is visibly present then the material is compressed between two slides and smeared. In case of completely evacuated cystic nodule, smears were prepared from the sediment. The clean slides are then labelled and studied under light microscopy. For Haematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and Papanicolaou (Pap) stain: 95% ethyl alcohol was used for fixation. For Leishman stain slides were air dried. When the surgery was done, the received specimens were fixed with 10% formalin and detailed gross examination was done and sections were taken from the representative areas for paraffin sections and stained by H & E. The sections were studied under light microscopy. Cytological diagnosis was correlated with histopathology whenever thyroidectomies were available.

Observations

A total of 100 thyroid lesions cases were included in the present study. Most of the cases 32(32%) were in age group of 41-50 years. Male and female ratio was 1:4.

According to FNAC diagnostic criteria, there were 62% benign cases, 9% malignant cases, 12% suspicious and 17% unsatisfactory or non-diagnosis. Benign lesions included 52(83.87%) cases of multinodular goiter, 8(12.90%) cases of Hashimoto's and Chronic non-specific lymphocytic thyroiditis, 1(1.62%) cases of Dequervain's subacute thyroiditis, and 1(1.62%) case of Riedel's thyroiditis.

Table 1: Age wise distribution of thyroid lesions patients.

Age group (Years)	No. of cases	Percentage
20-30	7	7%
31-40	26	26%
41-50	32	32%
51-60	22	22%
>60	13	13%
Total	100	100%

Figure 1: Gender wise distribution of thyroid lesions patients.

Table 2: Showing the FNAC results.

Benign	No. of cases	Malignant	No. of cases	Suspicious	No. of cases
Multi nodular goiter	52(83.87%)	Papillary ca.	5(55.56%)	Hurtle cell neoplasm	3(25%)
Hashimoto and NSLT	8(12.90%)	Follicular ca	1(11.11%)	Cystic papillary ca	2(16.67%)
De quervain thyroiditis	1(1.62%)	Medullary ca	1(11.11%)	Follicular neoplasm	7(58.33%)
Reidel thyroiditis	1(1.62%)	Other malignancies	2(22.22%)	-	-
Total	62(62%)		9(9%)		12(12%)

Seven (7) cases of benign category underwent surgery due to massive enlargement of thyroid and histopathologic examination was performed. The FNAC reports were confirmed in 4 cases by histopathologic examination, in remaining 1 patients FNAC reports were not confirmed, 1 case had papillary carcinoma, and one of them had follicular carcinoma in histopathologic examination. Therefore, in benign category, we had 4 true negative and 1 false negative results [table 3 & 4].

Out of 9 malignant lesions, papillary carcinoma was diagnosed in 5 cases, follicular carcinoma in 1 case, medullary carcinoma in 1 case and other malignancy present in 2 cases.

On histologic examination, 3 cases were diagnosed papillary carcinoma, 1 case had follicular carcinoma, 1 case had medullary carcinoma and one of them was diagnosed as NHL.

The cytopathologic diagnoses were confirmed by histopathologic examination in all of 2 cases which underwent surgery. Therefore, we had 2 true positive and 0 false positive in malignant group [table 3 & 4].

Of the 12 cases with suspicious results (table 3), 3 cases were suspected to have hurtle cell neoplasm, two cases suspected to have cystic papillary carcinoma, and the remainder 7 cases were follicular neoplasms that could not be differentiated from nodular hyperplasia.

In the present study, 13 patients underwent surgery. 2 cases of suspicious were ruled out. The 2 cases of medullary carcinoma, 2 cases of follicular carcinoma, and 3 case of papillary carcinoma. This group was not included in determining of FNAC accuracy [table 3 & 4].

Table 3: Showing the FNAC and histopathologic results.

FNAC diagnosis	Number of specimen	No. of patients with histological diagnosis	Histopathological		
			Benign	Malignant	Adenoma
Benign	62(62%)	7(11.29%)	4(TN)(6.45%)	1(FN)(1.61%)	0
Suspicious	12(12%)	3(25%)	1(8.33%)	1(8.33%)	3(25%)
Malignant	9(9%)	2(22.22%)	0(FP)	0	-
Inadequate	17(17%)	-	-		-
Total	100(100%)	12(12%)			

Table 4: Distribution of malignant cases among four FNAC categories.

Cytologic diagnosis	Histologic typing				Total
	Papillary Ca.	Follicular Ca	Medullary Ca.	Other malignancy	
Benign	1(20%)	1(25%)	-	-	2(15.39%)
Suspicious	1(20%)	1(25%)	-	-	2(15.39%)
Malignant	3(60%)	2(50%)	2(100%)	2(100)	9(69.23%)
Inadequate	-	-	-	-	-
Total	5(38.46%)	4(30.77%)	2(15.39%)	2(15.39%)	13(100%)

Discussions

The evaluation of patients with a thyroid nodule is essential due to the potentiality of malignancy; therefore, FNAC is a preferred, widely accepted diagnostic tool with high sensitivity and specificity rate. In the majority of the cases, it can differentiate benign from malignant nodules [8].

In the present study, 100 patients who underwent FNA for thyroid lesions were included, out of which 12 cases underwent thyroidectomies and were subjected to histopathological study. A comparison of various parameters in our present study was done with the other studies. The maximum number of cases 32(32%) were seen in the age group of 41- 50 years. Similar observations were seen by Manoj et al [9] and Yassa et al [10] observed maximum number of cases between age group of 41-50 years.

In the present study, maximum thyroid swellings were seen in female patients, with M:F ratio being 1:4. Similar observations were made by Silverman et al[11] found ratio was 1:6, Yassa et al[10] found was 1:7 and Rangaswamy et al[12] found was 1:3.

In the present study, maximum number of cases 52(83.87%) were seen in goitre group. Similar observations were seen by Manoj et al [9] (60%), Ray et al[13] (50%), Silverman et al [11] (56.5%) and GG Swamy et al[14] (50%). However, according to Rangaswamy et al [12] maximum cases came under follicular neoplasm 21 cases (44.68%).

On reviewing the histology slides, there were seen focal areas of dilated papillae filled with colloid and probably the aspiration needle has not hit that site. This can be avoided by aspirating from multiple sites of glands. Our case even on respiration only colloid material was seen. Since most of the papillary carcinomas undergo cystic degeneration and cystic papillary carcinomas yield fluid aspirate with scant follicular cells, which masks the diagnosis of papillary carcinoma giving a false negative result [15]. Braga M et al found that cystic thyroid nodules are considered to be one of the major causes of non-diagnostic and false negative results on conventional fine needle aspiration, thus limiting the potential of this method for the evaluation of complex thyroid nodules. Ultrasound guided fine needle aspiration

cytology is suggested as an excellent modality for the evaluation of the complex nodules and also for the re-evaluation of those nodules with non-diagnostic result on the conventional fine needle aspiration [16]. Goellner JR in his study commented that cyst fluid showing no pathologic change and containing only degenerative foam cells should be interpreted as “non-diagnostic” rather than “negative” [17].

In the present study, 52 cases of nodular goitre were diagnosed by fine needle aspiration cytology out of which 4 cases histopathologically proved to be nodular goitre. Out of remaining 1 case turn out to malignancy. Silverman JF et al [11] in their study of 36 cases of Follicular neoplasm on FNAC, 27 cases were confirmed on histopathology with a diagnostic accuracy of 75%. Another study done by Hall TL et al [18] in their study of 17 cases of Follicular neoplasm on FNAC, 10 cases were confirmed on histopathology with a diagnostic accuracy of 58.8%. This less diagnostic accuracy is explained by the fact that, there always exist confusion between hyperplastic nodular goitre and follicular adenoma. This error is generally accepted as unavoidable because of cytomorphologic similarity and the need to maintain a high degree of sensitivity to the presence of a neoplastic process requiring surgical biopsy.

In the present study, 3 out of 5 cases were correctly diagnosed papillary carcinoma on FNAC with a diagnostic accuracy of 60%. Papillary thyroid carcinoma is the most common malignant tumor of the thyroid. Its pathological diagnosis is based on classic nuclear features. Although majority of papillary cancers can be diagnosed and classified on the basis of set pathological criteria, there exists a group of cases in which benign thyroid tissue or lesions can mimic nuclear cytologic features or the architecture and growth pattern of papillary thyroid cancers, posing a diagnostic problem. Hall TL et al [18] found diagnostic accuracy of 89.6%, Gagnetten CB et al [19] found 80% and Gupta M et al [9] found 75% diagnostic accuracy of papillary carcinoma on FNAC.

Papillary formations can occur as a focal change or in the form of a dominant nodule in multinodular goitre, Hashimoto’s thyroiditis and Graves disease. These papillary patterned lesions can be partly or totally composed of oncocytic cells and show

complex papillae with well-formed vascular cores or stroma poor edematous papillae with subfollicles. Fine needle aspirations of cytology specimens of solitary papillary hyperplastic nodules demonstrate cellular smears, transgressing vessels, papillary clusters, nuclear atypia, and pleomorphism, the presence of Intranuclear grooves, multinucleated giant cells and cells with vacuolated cytoplasm. In view of these features, such cases could be misclassified as “suspicious of” or consistent with papillary carcinoma. However, in our case cytological features which mimicked papillary carcinoma features were having high cellularity, papillary clusters with anatomical borders, presence of Intranuclear inclusions and multinucleated giant cells [20].

Baloch et al. [21] had done a comparison study between FNAC and histopathology of thyroid lesion and found that the accuracy and FNAC were 91.6% which is similar to the accuracy calculated in our study (85.3%). In a study similar to ours carried out by Handa et al. [5], FNAC showed sensitivity of 97%, specificity 100%, a positive predictive value of 96% and a negative predictive value of 100%. Rout et al. reported the accuracy of thyroid swelling to be 96.05% [22]. A similar study conducted by Mundasat et al. has reported the accuracy of FNAC to be 79.1% for thyroid malignancy [23]. Hence, there is a significant disparity in thyroid FNAC statistics. This may be due to an insufficient number of cases, diagnostic categories used and different classifications systems used by the cytopathologists. Vast experience is needed in performing a proper aspiration to get adequate material.

Conclusions

The present study concluded that the thyroid lesions are preponderance to old age female as compared to male population. FNAC is the best choice first line diagnostic test and effective screening tool for the diagnosis and management of patients with thyroid lesions.

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